

THE SEED FAT OF *BUCHANANIA LATIFOLIA**

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The component fatty acids of *Buchanania Latifolia* seed fat were found to be : palmitic 29%, stearic 8%, oleic 57% and linoleic 6% (by weight). It contains 4.8% of fully saturated glycerides. The glyceride structure of the fat follows the usual rule of "even distribution "

Buchanania latifolia, Roxb. (N.O Anacardiaceæ) (Indian name—Chironji), is a very common tree of the Indian forests. It bears in summer cherry like fruits, of which the upper thin skin and the seed enclosed in a hard round shell are edible. The seeds, light brown in colour, are very commonly used in confectionery, while the oil from the seeds is used as a substitute for almond oil for medicinal purposes. The seed, as well as the oil are recommended for cure of certain skin diseases by Indian physicians.

Of the seed fats belonging to this family (Anacardiaceæ) only those mentioned below seem to have been analysed so far for their component fatty acid content.

(a) *Pistacia vera* (Dhingra and Hilditch, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1931, 80, gr).

(b) *Antrocaryon Nannani* (Pieraerts and Ipatiev, *Mat. grasscs*, 1927, 19, 7974).

(c) *Anacardium Occidentale* (Patel, Sudborough and Watson, *J. Ind., Inst. Sci.*, 1923, 6, III).

From the present study, as well as from the analyses of the above fats it would be seen that in general, the predominating acids occurring in the seed fats of this family are palmitic, oleic and linoleic and in some cases stearic. Schaedler, ("Technologie der Fett und Öle," II, p. 668) and Bolton and Jesson (*Analyst*, 1915, 40, 3) have reported only the characteristic values of the oil from the seeds of *Buchanania latifolia* which along with the values of the present sample, are given in Table I.

It appears from Table I that although the three samples do not differ very much, the sample now analysed resembles more with the one reported by Schaedler.

* From the thesis submitted by P. D. Srivastava, for D.Sc. of the Benares Hindu University.

TABLE I.

Characteristics.	Schaedler.	Bolton & Jesson.	Present work.
Sp. gr. 30°/30°	—	—	0.9232
Melting point	32°	—	Liquid at room temp. (about 25°)
Solidification point	—	18°	—
Refractive index (40°)	—	—	1.4572
Acid value	15.4	51.8	32.7
Saponification value	193.6	198.7	193.2
Iodine value	57.3	55.0	62.4
R. M. value	0.33	—	—
Acetyl value	—	—	4.5
Unsaponifiables	—	2.15	1.07
Hehner value	—	—	93.1

EXPERIMENTAL.

The seeds (1 kg.), obtained from the local market, were cleaned, powdered and extracted with light petroleum (b. p. 40°-60°) in a Soxhlet apparatus. This gave 500 g. (50%) of a pale yellow fixed oil having a mild but agreeable aroma.

Another portion of 500 g. of the same powdered seeds was extracted with benzene, petroleum ether being not available. In this case the oil obtained (240 g., 48%) was of rather deeper colour and even after prolonged heating under reduced pressure, the smell of benzene could not be totally removed.

Both these samples of chironji fat, after dehydration and filtration, were separately examined for their general characteristics, given in Table II.

TABLE II.

	Extract.		Mixed sample.
	Petroleum ether	Benzene.	
Acid value	32.4	33.2	32.7
Saponification value	193.1	188.4	193.2
Iodine value	61.5	59.4	63.4

Since both the samples did not differ much (low sap. value of benzene extracted fat might be due to the presence of traces of the solvent) these were mixed for the present study. The characteristic values of the mixed sample are also given in Table II. In winter (room temp. 20-25°) a part

of the fat was found crystallising, suggesting the possibility of the presence of fully saturated or disaturated-mono-unsaturated glycerides. It was, therefore, considered worth while to study the glyceride structure of the fat along with the component fatty acids.

For the estimation of glycerides it was necessary to remove the free fatty acids from the fat. The fat (450 g.) was dissolved in four times its volume of ether and the solution treated twice with excess of 10% solution of potassium carbonate. The ethereal solution, washed free from alkali, on removing ether, gave 400 g. of neutral fat (S. E., 291·4; A. V., 0·0; I. V., 54·1). From the potassium carbonate washings 46 g. of fatty acids (S. E., 272·5; I. V., 59·7) were recovered. It would be seen from the characteristics of these recovered acids that these have a composition almost similar to that of component fatty acids of the neutral fat.

Component Acids.

The neutral oil (112 g.) was hydrolysed and the recovered fatty acids (103 g.) (S. E., 274·8; I. V., 61·8) were then separated into 'solid' (36·65%) and 'liquid' (63·35%) acids by means of the different solubility of their lead salts in alcohol (Hilditch *et al.*, *Biochem. J.*, 1929, 23, 327). Each group of acids was then converted into the corresponding methyl esters which were fractionally distilled under vacuum (0·5-1·0 mm.) from a Willstätter bulb. The fractionation data are given in Tables III and IV.

TABLE III.

Fractional distillation of methyl esters of the solid acids 'S'.

Fraction No.	Esters (S. E. = 275·1; I. V. = 4·2)			
	Wt.	B. p.	S. E.	I. V.
S ₁	3·23 g.	124°-38°	270·1	0·6
S ₂	3·07	138°	270·5	0·6
S ₃	4·01	138°-39°	274·0	2·3
S ₄	4·88	140°	274·5	2·5
S ₅	3·58	140°-43°	274·8	3·7
S ₆	3·71	143°-46°	275·8	5·5
S ₇	2·41	Falling	279·0	7·6
S ₈	4·79	Residue	199·8	13·5
	<u>29·68</u>			

TABLE IV.

Fractional distillation of methyl esters of the liquid acids 'L'.

Fraction No.	Esters 'S. E. = 297'5; I. V. = 87'4)		S. E.	I. V.
	Wt.	B. p.		
L ₁	2'60 g.	115°-35°	289'5	74'10
L ₂	5'72	135°-50°	292'5	83'60
L ₃	3'66	150°-52°	294'7	89'80
L ₄	6'30	152°	295'0	90'00
L ₅	8'86	152°-56°	295'1	91'2
L ₆	8'32	156°-58°	295'2	93'6
L ₇	3'92	156°-58°	295'2	93'4
L ₈	2'67	Falling	295'1	93'20
L ₉	5'69	Residue	308'0	81'7
	47'74			

Examination of Individual Ester Fractions.

Fractions S₁, S₂.—Acids obtained from these fractions melted at 62°. On recrystallisation from alcohol (90%), the melting point rose to 62'5°. The presence of palmitic acid was thus confirmed.

Fraction S₃.—The residual fraction S₃ contained acids which, when freed from the unsaponifiable matter, had S. E., 279'4; I. V., 9'2. These acids when crystallised from acetone melted at 68°. This melting point remained unchanged on further crystallisations from acetone, thus indicating the absence of any acid higher than stearic.

Fraction L₉.—After removing the unsaponifiable matter the acids obtained from this fraction had S. E. 277'3 and I. V., 76'2.

Fractions L₆—L₉.—About 5 g. of the acids from these fractions were brominated in ethereal solution at 5° and allowed to stand at 0° for a long time, but no insoluble bromide separated. Linolenic acid is therefore absent. The residue from the above after removing ether was crystallised from light petroleum, when only a small amount of a crystalline product (m. p. 110°) separated indicating thereby the presence of ordinary seed fat linoleic acid.

A portion (about 3 g.) of the acids from fractions L₈—L₉ was oxidised in solution in dilute alkali at 0° by potassium permanganate, and the

products of oxidation extracted with light petroleum to remove any saturated acids. The products insoluble in light petroleum were separated by hot water into an insoluble and a soluble portion. The former yielded, on crystallisation from ethyl acetate, an acid m. p. 131° (mixed m. p. with 9: 10-dihydroxystearic acid, 132°), while the residue obtained from the latter portion was too small for further examination. Presence of ordinary oleic acid was thus confirmed.

With the help of the above qualitative examination and the ester fractionation data given in Tables III and IV, the component acids of the fat of *B. Latifolia* are calculated (Table V).

TABLE V.

Acids.	Solid (36·65%).	Liquid (63·35%).	Total.	Fatty acids (ex-non-sap).	
				(%wt).	(%mol).
Myristic	—	0·14	0·14	0·1	0·2
Palmitic	26·54	2·19	28·73	28·9	30·9
Stearic	8·08	—	8·08	8·1	7·8
Oleic	1·90	55·15	57·05	57·4	55·7
Linoleic	—	5·44	5·44	5·5	5·4
Unsaponifiables	0·13	0·43	0·56	—	—

Component Glycerides.

The fully saturated glycerides (F. S. G.) of the fat were determined by the acetone-permanganate oxidation method. Oxidation was carried out in two batches A and B (53. 1 g. and 75 g. respectively). The fat was dissolved in dry acetone (10 c.c. per g.) and oxidised with powdered potassium permanganate (4 g. per g. of fat). Batch A gave 2·48 g. of crude F. S. G. with A. V., 0·8; I. V., 1·3; whence % F. S. G. would be 4·4% (wt); while from batch B, 3·82 g. of crude F. S. G. with S.E., 276·2; A. V., 1·0; I. V., 1·2, were obtained, [whence % F. S. G., 4·8% (wt)]. It, therefore, follows that the fat contains 4·6% (wt) or 4·8% (mol.) of fully saturated glycerides. The acids, freed from the unsaponifiable matter, from the F. S. G. had S. E., 262·3.

From the above data and from those given in Table V for the whole fat, the distribution of the component fatty acids in the fully saturated and the mixed saturated-unsaturated parts of the fat is calculated as given in Table VI.

TABLE VI.

Balance sheet (molecular).

Acid.	Whole fat (100 mols.)	F. S. G. (4·8 mols.)	Mixed part 95·2 mols (by diff.).	
Palmitic	31·1*	3·9	27·2	} 34·1
Stearic	7·6	0·9	6·9	
Oleic	55·7	—	55·7	} 61·1
Linoleic	5·4	—	5·4	

Association ratio (saturated: unsaturated) in the mixed part 0·56: 1

* This includes 0·2% of myristic also.

Thus the major component acids of *B. Latifolia* fat are palmitic and oleic, stearic and linoleic being only in small proportions. As may be expected from this composition and with due consideration to the well established 'rule of even distribution' (Hilditch *et al, loc. cit.*) the amount of fully saturated glycerides present is small. The component glycerides of the fully saturated part would be (calculated from its S. E.) tripalmitin (2·1 mols.) and steardipalmitin (2·7 mols.) For the mixed part two alternative combinations of glycerides are possible :

(a) Mono-saturated-di-unsaturated, (88·1 mols.) and disaturated-mono-unsaturated (7·1 mols) and (b) disaturated-mono-unsaturated (51·2 mols.) and triunsaturated (44·0 mols.) Of these the former combination (a) is more likely to be present according to the rule of even distribution. Since the amount of the fat was small, detailed glyceride structure estimation by crystallisation method could not be done. The present data are, however, sufficient to show the general distribution of the fatty acids in the glycerides of the fat.